

THE USE OF SMARTPHONES AND APPS TO IMPROVE ENGLISH LEARNERS' SKILLS IN THE CLASSROOM

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Abstract: *Nowadays. In this high-tech world technology is getting more advanced so that it impacts on every sphere of life including education, especially, learning and teaching English. Modern innovative technologies in the educational process increase the quality and effectiveness of education. In particular, there are several ways to use such information and communication technologies in learning and teaching a foreign language. Its advantages give important opportunity to make learning process more effective. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is immeasurable. It is famously used all over the world that technical devices such as IWB, Smart phones, Internet, Apps are able to grab everyone's attention and respect since its great contribution in the achievement of learning and teaching language is limitless.*

Key words: *Technology, gadgets, motivation, 21st century skills, smartphones, learning apps.*

Introduction: Technology users in fundamental structural changes that can be integral to achieving significant improvements in productivity. Used to support both teaching and learning, technology infuses classrooms with digital learning tools, such as computers and hand held devices; expands course offerings, experiences, and learning materials; supports learning 24 hours a day, 7 days a week; builds 21st century skills; increases student engagement and motivation; and accelerates learning. Technology also has the power to transform teaching by ushering in a new model of connected teaching. This model links teacher to their students and to professional content, resources, and systems to help them improve their own instruction and personalize learning.

Smartphones are the most powerful technological gadgets of the current time and its multi-functional features have made it a very important part of the everyday routine for almost all people. Smartphones play a very significant role in almost every-thing an individual does in the day to day work. It is recognized as an important tool of work, entertainment, learning, teaching, etc. In addition to its effectiveness in different aspects of life, smartphones have also been recognized as an important educational tool

that facilitates both learning and teaching process in the field of education. According to mobile technology is considered to be the recognized face of educational applications for the recent technologies. Although, many colleges and institutions did not welcome the use of smartphones by students during school hours previously and its use was recognized as a disruption for students' learning, however, with the vast beneficial features that smartphones offer specifically for the benefit of learning and teaching, educators and policy makers in the field of education are already recognizing the smartphones as a powerful educational tool that could be used both by the students and teachers to facilitate their learning or teaching process. In addition, students of the 21st century are so much attached to the technological trends and it would be hard for them to even imagine not using it in their everyday life. According to students in colleges cannot stand it longer without checking their technological devices such as smartphones, laptops etc. When it comes to technology, students are the usually the first to jump into it and try the new technology and it is most likely that they would do innovation in finding new ways of utilizing the available technology, thus the study of smartphone use among students has to be of particular significance.

Methodology: In order to achieve the goal of this article, over 10 articles which are related to the topic have been investigated. The researcher adopts descriptive and empirical analytical approaches as far as data collection and discussion are concerned. Moreover, in order to compare academic writing and text language, the comparative method is utilized.

Results and Discussions: However, mobile phones in the classroom have always been a controversial topic. Some teachers worry about the potential for student distraction, while others have decided to use them because they offer some positive learning benefits. The reality is that students, especially those ages 12-18, use smartphones on a daily basis. For most, smartphones are their device of choice, and nearly all 95% of all teens have them (Pew Research, 2018). Because this device is so commonplace, it makes sense to leverage its benefits.

Furthermore, mobile phones and apps can help students to improve their vocabulary. As we all know, advantages of technology are more cheap, comfortable, modern, fast, effective, reliable and interactive than traditional way. Moreover, during the learning process learners have an opportunity to be good working with computer. They are able to communicate easily and clearly. The more use appropriate words during their speech the better listener can understand them. Additionally, it is not so difficult to express their feelings, opinions and knowledge at the second language if they have enlarged vocabulary. It is irrefutable fact that technology is getting increase more and more in every sphere of our life nowadays, as well as educational system, especially, in

language learning. Furthermore, the government pays great attention to develop ICT in educational system. It can be reasonable proof that the first President I. Karimov declared a law which was about creating informational portal, Ziyonet, on September 28, 2005. As a result, using technology helps improve quality of education, moreover, inventions of 21 century give a chance learners to make their learning process easy and effective. In addition, these days English language learners can't imagine the learning procedure without gadgets, digital tools, internet, computer and multimedia. They are also extremely helpful to expand range of vocabulary. Actually, even within modern developing visual world, words play a role as a primary means of communication. It is demandable that learners should have enough vocabulary to become an effective language learner. It is real fact that using multimedia is not so complicated to learn new words by heart. So, there are a number of ways to improve vocabulary by using mobile devices. They are:

Using mobile phones. Using mobile phones can provide comfortable and effective atmosphere of studying words for three reasons. At the first place learners can expand their vocabulary by listening, records in their mobile phones, According to human being's nature young people tend to listen to music so that learners may record new words in their devices as their favorite and adorable songs or music. And then they can listen and sing those records. Perfect proof of how this strategy is useful is a film "Ron Clark" which is about a skillful school teacher. That teacher creates a new lyric which consists of numerous and difficult to memorize names and years of Presidents of USA for modern music. As a result, his students do their best during exams. At the second place, by changing language of mobile phones into English, learners can learn new technical words unplanned way when they come across those words a lot. Moreover, learners can save name of people linked with new words, for example, if learners should learn the word "Stubborn", they can save name of person who is stubborn by nature. At the third place learners can utilize e-dictionary instead of real dictionary books. E-dictionary does not only help to find new words easily and quickly, but also can provide with pronunciation of those words.

Using online websites and vocabulary software of games. Internet consists of majority of online websites to learn English autonomously. Generally speaking, some learners do not have ability to know what they should do or learn for their improvement. At that time, websites can be helpful for them. English websites provide very essential and important words for English learners. In that websites, not only learners can learn new words, but can check their pronunciation too. Additionally, those websites have a great supply of useful tests, handouts crossword puzzles and so forth. Those websites do not demand to waste time and money to go somewhere; learners just sit in a corner of the

room and can gain knowledge as the same with ordinary tutor classes. Some suggested websites are MyEnglishTeacher.eu on Facebook, Babble, and English Vocabulary Dictionary (created by MyEnglishTeacher.eu itself)

Secondly, most of people have come up with different solutions and ideas which are a bit boring to expand vocabulary. But what about the joy of playing games in learning process? It has been proven by several experiments that playing games have their important role in learning process. Because when learners are bored in reading, writing words, they can play interesting games on their mobile phones even in crowded bus or taxi conveniently. As we know the objects which are remembered every day are more memorable (2). On the other hand, there are a number of advantages to play games in learning process:

- Learners do not get bored
- Learners can keep their time properly (instead of playing different games they play English games at the time they want to play something on their mobile phones)
- Speed and quality of learning process is getting better by learning from visual and audio materials.
- Learners can be motivated by relax able music, different pictures and funny figures of games.

In fact, there are majority of games in Google play. Some suggested games are Learn English Vocabulary, Vocabulary Builder, Power Vocabulary Word Game, Volt Vocabulary

3. Using computers. While reaching top of improvement, computer is also advisable tool. Learners can watch English movies or different videos related to specific topics. It is a true fact that just learning new words by heart is not enough to enlarge vocabulary. The less the words are used in real life, the more they are forgotten. According to traditional way of teaching when we learn words we make a list of new words in our notebook. The main problem with learning new words is vocabulary list. Because we just focus on what words mean. But when we watch film learners can learn where and how words are used in reality. For example, learners learn “king” word. As we know from dictionary, it is “a man who rules a country because he is from a royal family (Longman dictionary)”. But if learners learn the word “King” through watching films, it can be a title in front of a person (e.g King Arthur). On the other hand, “King” is used in idiom like “a king’s ransom” which means “a very large amount of money”. This way learners do not only learn what each word means, but also how it is used. Moreover, it is useful to watch film with subtitle, because there are many words which express feeling or sound such as murmur, twinkle. When something is twinkling in the

film, the word “twinkling” is written with brackets and learners can understand and memorize easily. In this technological world, every person should invite digital tools into their business because of being efficient and unique way to develop quickly. Briefly speaking, using technology supports confident atmosphere of learning, active, interesting, encouraging learning in words that are essential to vocabulary development. Additionally, having idea how to use technology is main factor of becoming successful and strategic learner.

Literacy games and apps are also available online and for downloading, as well as reviews of educational software apps. Another great resource is a large variety of online books, often organized by subject, with the text and photos of each page easily seen on the screen by the student, who can click on the arrow to turn the page. For students who may not be keen on reading but love computers, online books can be useful teaching tool, as well as providing an easy way for a teacher to improve the classroom library. A great related feature of several websites is the information they support about the authors and illustrators of students’ books. Pupils in our classrooms, the use of online applications is second nature. All we, as teachers and ICT coordinators, need do is introduce them to the on line apps that can help unlock their creativity and collaborative skills- and help their study, revision and organization.

Moreover, new interactive games are being created by programmers more an more. For instance, Kahoot! This online quiz game is wonderful quiz tool for teachers to create awesome game for students. It grabs students’ attention through colourful quizzes and wide range of questions. Actually, Kahoot! is a game-based learning platform that brings engagement and fun to players every year at school, at work, and at home. This game is great example of knowing how apps and smartphones can be great teaching tools. Here are some photos of Kahoot!

Another wonderful app to use while teaching and learning English is “Cake”. This software program is famous for its specialized videos on each topic and explanation of every idiom. Teachers can use it to improve their students’ speaking and pronunciation, moreover it helps learners to speak like native speakers, since there are tons of videos explaining idioms which are used in everyday English in natural way. On the top of that, videos in Cake is not so long and boring, moreover it is with subtitles and have interesting and attention grabbing content in each video. Besides that it is totally free of charge to use and download, which means that everybody has access to use it. Here are some pictures:

The list of used literature:

1. Uzoqova Xayriniso (2023) Opportunities of internet in teaching english in the classroom, International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers
2. Tilavova, M. (2020). Language is a bridge to the wonders of the world. Журнал дошкольного образования, (1).
3. Nizomova, Z. (2020). Teachers' English Proficiency and classroom language use. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 1(1), 92-96.
4. Tilavova, M. (2021). The Impact of Motivation In Learning Foreign Languages. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 4(9).
5. Nizomova, Z. (2023). Analysis of english alliteration as a stylistic device, International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers